

NONCLASSICAL STRESS-STRAIN STATE MODELS IN PROBLEMS OF MECHANICS OF LAYERED BEAMS

V.G.Piskunov and B.V.Grynevitsky

National Transport University, Kiev, Ukraine
E-mail: ksmm@ntu.edu.ua

ABSTRACT: a nonclassical analytical model of stress-strain state of composite beams with the account of the shear deformation is proposed. The beam has the piece-heterogeneous structure along the height. The normal and tangential loads are acted on the top and on the bottom surfaces, and on the surfaces between the layers. The model is decelerated the distribution of the tangential displacement through the thickness as the third degree polynomial. The system of the differential equation is obtained by the variation method and consists two equations. The first equation is the analogy of the equation of the beam classical theory for the normal displacement. The second equation is the analogy of the equation of the beam classical theory for the bending moment are excited the generalize load. The testing problems are given the comparison with three-dimensional solution and the experimental dates and for the supported and clamped beams different composite structure. As the practical engineering problem is given the solution for the many supported static indefinable layered beam.

KEYWORDS: analytical model, composite beams, shear deformation, piece-heterogeneous, comparative results.

The analytical shear (nonclassical) models of the stress-strain state of heterogeneous layered structures described, for example, in reviews [1–6] have been widely used to solve various problems [7–10]. However, the solution of bending problems for structures, in particular, composite layered beams with various boundary conditions under arbitrary loads, is rather complicated. In the present study, based on the nonclassical shear model of layered beams constructed earlier, relations of a simplified variant of the model are derived, which remove these complications in large measure.

1. Theoretical preconditions for the model. Let us construct a variant of the refined model for calculating layered beams (Fig. 1)

Fig.1. Scheme layered beam

The system of differential equations derived in [9] by the variation method has the form

$$D_{11} \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} + D_{12} \frac{d^4 \chi}{dx^4} = Q_1, \quad D_{12} \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} + D_{22} \frac{d^4 \chi}{dx^4} - D_{12} \frac{d^2 \chi}{dx^2} = Q_2, \quad (1)$$

where $w(x)$ and $\chi(x)$ are the sought-for functions of deflection and shear; D_{11} , D_{22} and D_{12} are the generalized rigidities of the beam in bending and shear and in the interaction of its layers, respectively. In addition, we have introduced here some characteristics combining the normal $q_z(x)$ and tangential $q_x(x)$ loads applied to the external surfaces and the interfaces:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_1 &= \sum_{i=0}^n q_z^{(i)} c_z^{(i)} + D_{13} \frac{d^3 Q_n}{dx^3} - D_{14} \frac{d^3 Q_k}{dx^3} - \xi_0 \frac{dQ'_n}{dx}, \\ Q_2 &= D_{23} \frac{d^3 Q_n}{dx^3} - D_{24} \frac{d^3 Q_k}{dx^3} - \xi_1 \frac{dQ'_n}{dx} - \bar{D}_1 \frac{dQ_n}{dx} + \bar{D}_2 \frac{dQ_k}{dx}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where

$$Q_n = \left(\frac{1}{b_n} \right) \left[\sum_{i=0}^n q_x^{(i)} c_x^{(i)} \right], \quad Q_k = \left(\frac{1}{b_k} \right) \left[\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} q_x^{(i)} c_x^{(i)} \right], \quad Q'_n = \sum_{i=0}^n q_x^{(i)} c_x^{(i)},$$

and $c_x^{(i)}$ and $c_z^{(i)}$ are the widths of the areas of application of corresponding loads; D_{13} , D_{14} , D_{23} and D_{24} are the generalized rigidities associated with the account of operating loads; ξ_0 and ξ_1 are the distribution functions of loading characteristics over its height of beam cross section, which allow for its layered structure and the physic mechanical properties of layer materials.

We transform the system of equations (1) to the identical form

$$D_{11} \frac{d^4}{dx^4} \left(w + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \chi \right) = Q_1, \quad D_{12} \frac{d^4}{dx^4} \left(w + \frac{D_{22}}{D_{12}} \chi \right) - D_{12} \frac{d^2 \chi}{dx^2} = Q_2. \quad (3)$$

From the results of calculating the rigidities, we get the following relations:

$$\frac{D_{22}}{D_{12}} \approx \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}}, \quad \frac{D_{13}}{D_{11}} = \frac{D_{23}}{D_{12}}, \quad \frac{D_{14}}{D_{11}} = \frac{D_{24}}{D_{12}}. \quad (4)$$

The account of relations (4) in system (3) makes it possible to reduce the latter to the form

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} \left(w + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \chi \right) = \frac{Q_1}{D_{11}}, \quad \frac{d^4}{dx^4} \left(w + \frac{D_{22}}{D_{12}} \chi \right) - \frac{d^2 \chi}{dx^2} = \frac{Q_2}{D_{12}}, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d^4}{dx^4} \left(w + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \chi \right) = \frac{Q_1}{D_{11}}, \quad \frac{d^2 \chi}{dx^2} = \frac{Q_1}{D_{11}} - \frac{Q_2}{D_{12}}, \quad (6)$$

After introduction of the new generalized function of displacements

$$\Phi = \left(w + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \chi \right),$$

system (5) takes the form

$$\frac{d^4 \Phi}{dx^4} = \frac{Q_1}{D_{11}}, \quad \frac{d^2 \chi}{dx^2} = Q_{12}, \quad \text{where} \quad Q_{12} = \frac{1}{D_{11}} \left(Q_1 - Q_2 \frac{D_{11}}{D_{12}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Based on the general boundary conditions at beam ends ($x = 0, x = l$) given in [9] and function (6), we write the following conditions:

- for hinge support

$$\Phi = 0; \quad \frac{d^2\Phi}{dx^2} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{D_{13}Q_n - D_{14}Q_k}{D_{11}} \right); \quad \chi = 0. \quad (8)$$

- for rigid clamping

$$\Phi = 0, \quad d\Phi/dx = 0, \quad \chi = 0. \quad (9)$$

- for one of the free ends of the beam

$$\frac{d^2\Phi}{dx^2} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{D_{13}Q_n - D_{14}Q_k}{D_{11}} \right), \quad \frac{d^3\Phi}{dx^3} = \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(\frac{D_{13}Q_n - D_{14}Q_k}{D_{11}} \right) - Q'_n \psi_0(z),$$

$$\frac{d\chi}{dx} = \frac{Q_n \bar{D}_1 - Q_k \bar{D}_2 - Q'_n [\psi_1(z) - \psi_0(z)]}{D_{12}}. \quad (10)$$

In the absence of tangential loads, these conditions are simplified:

- hinge support $\Phi = 0, \quad d^2\Phi/dx^2 = 0, \quad \chi = 0;$
- rigid clamping $\Phi = 0, \quad d\Phi/dx = 0, \quad \chi = 0;$
- free end $d^2\Phi/dx^2 = 0, \quad d^3\Phi/dx^3 = 0, \quad d\chi/dx = 0.$

A comparison of the system of equations (7) and boundary conditions (11) with the equations and conditions for the problem of bending of a beam according to the classical (engineering) model shows that the function $\Phi = \Phi(x)$ is an analogue of is function of the classical deflection $w_{cl} = w_{cl}(x)$ and the function $\chi = \chi(x)$ is an analogue of the function of the beam bending moment $M_{cl}^* = M_{cl}^*(x)$ from the conditional load $Q_1^* = -\frac{Q_1}{D_{11}}$. With regard for these analogies, conditions (11) at the am ends have the following forms:

- hinge support – $w_{cl} = 0, \quad \frac{d^2w_{cl}}{dx^2} = 0, \quad M_{cl}^* = 0;$
- rigid clamping – $w_{cl} = 0, \quad \frac{dw_{cl}}{dx} = 0, \quad M_{cl}^* = 0;$
- free end – $\frac{d^2w_{cl}}{dx^2} = 0, \quad \frac{d^3w_{cl}}{dx^3} = 0, \quad \frac{dM_{cl}^*}{dx} = 0.$

Thus, the solution to the bending problem for a beam, according to the variant of the refined model, is reduced to the equations of the classical model in terms of deflections and the above-mentioned bending moments. In this case, the function of deflection is defined as the sum of the classical deflection and the component due to shear deformations:

$$w = w_{cl} - \left(\frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \right) M_{cl}^* = w_{cl} + w_{sh}. \quad (13)$$

The normal stresses are described by the expression

$$\sigma_x^{(k)} = -E_k \left[\frac{d^2w_{cl}}{dx^2} \xi_0^{(k)}(z) - \frac{d^2M_{cl}^*}{dx^2} \left(\xi_0^{(k)}(z) \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} - \xi_1^{(k)}(z) \right) \right]. \quad (14)$$

2. Test problems. The suggested variant of the refined model was tested for reliability. Based on the above-mentioned theoretical relations, we obtained solutions for the function of deflection along the beam under a sinusoidal load

$$w(x) = w_0 \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{l}\right); \quad w_0 = \left[\sum_{i=0}^n q_{z0}^{(i)} c_z^{(i)} \right] \frac{1}{D_{11}} \left[1 + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \frac{\pi^2}{l^2} \right] \frac{l^4}{\pi^4}, \quad (15)$$

and expressions for the normal and tangential stresses

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x^{(k)}(x, z) &= E_k \left[\sum_{i=0}^n q_{z0}^{(i)} c_z^{(i)} \right] \frac{1}{D_{11}} \frac{l^2}{\pi^2} \sin \frac{\pi x}{l} \left[\xi_1(z) - \xi_0(z) \left(\frac{l^2}{\pi^2} + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \right) \right], \\ \tau_{zx}^{(k)}(x, z) &= \left[\sum_{i=0}^n q_{z0}^{(i)} c_z^{(i)} \right] \frac{1}{D_{11}} \frac{\pi}{l} \cos \frac{\pi x}{l} \left[F_0(z) \left(\frac{l^2}{\pi^2} + \frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}} \right) - F_1(z) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $F_0(z)$ and $F_1(z)$ are the distribution functions of tangential stresses over the height of beam cross section.

To compare the calculation results according to the classical, nonclassical, and three-dimensional [14] models, we considered the problem of bending of a three-layer beam (Fig. 2) with the characteristics presented in Table 1. The materials of the layers of the beam were transversely isotropic. The shear module of the less rigid middle layer ($k=2$) and the relative length l/h were varied. The amplitude of the sinusoidal load was $q_{z0} = 50$ kN/m.

Fig. 2. Structure three-layered beam

TABLE 1. Characteristics of Layer Materials of a Three-Layer Beam

Layer number, k	Layer width b , m	Layer height h_k , m	Elastic module E_k , MPa	Shear module G_k' , MPa
1	0.01	0.03	10^4	360
2	0.01	0.06	940	360(36)
1	0.01	0.03	10^4	360

The results of comparing the basic components of the stress-strain state are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Calculation Results of a Three-Layer Beam

Model	Shear modulus G'_2 , MPa	l/h					
		10		5		3	
<i>Deflections</i>		w , mm	n_w	w , mm	n_w	w , mm	n_w
Classical	360	8,336	1,234	0,521	1,931	0,068	3,560
Nonclassical		10,283		1,006		0,240	
Three-dimensional		10,270	1,232	1,008	1,935	0,247	3,661
Nonclassical	36	22,212	2,665	3,492	6,702	0,865	12,82
Three-dimensional		22,222	2,666	3,523	6,762	0,917	13,58
<i>Normal Stresses</i>		σ , MPa	n_σ	σ , MPa	n_σ	σ , MPa	n_σ
Classical	360	-34,278	1,031	-8,570	1,125	-3,085	1,343
Nonclassical		-35,352		-9,638		-4,143	
Three-dimensional		-35,250	1,028	-9,552	1,115	-4,081	1,323
Nonclassical	36	-46,576	1,359	-19,010	2,229	-10,940	3,546
Three-dimensional		-46,330	1,352	-18,637	2,175	-10,440	3,384
<i>Tangential Stresses</i>		τ , MPa	n_τ	τ , MPa	n_τ	τ , MPa	n_τ
Classical	360	2,082	0,996	1,0412	0,985	0,6247	0,960
Nonclassical		2,075		1,026		0,600	
Three-dimensional		2,076	0,997	1,029	0,988	0,606	0,970
Nonclassical	36	1,939	0,931	0,796	0,764	0,320	0,512
Three-dimensional		1,943	0,933	0,813	0,781	0,360	0,575

In Table 2, n_w , n_σ and n_τ are ratios between the deflections and the normal and tangential stresses obtained from the nonclassical model and the exact three-dimensional solution of elasticity theory and the corresponding deflections and stresses according to the classical model. An analysis of the data in Table 2 shows that, with decreasing shear modulus in the middle layer, the ratios n_w , n_σ and n_τ increase; in particular, for deflections at $l/h = 3$, the ratio n_w increases 3,6 times. The ratios for normal stresses on the upper (loaded) surface increases 2.64 times.

The results obtained at $l/h = 3$ are shown in Fig. 3 in the form of diagrams according to the classical (dashed line) and nonclassical (continuous line) models. Attention is drawn by the considerable distinction in the deflections obtained from these models and in the character of stress distribution at different shear module of the middle layer. As to the distribution of normal stresses across the beam thickness, their values obtained from the nonclassical model, at a smaller shear modulus of the middle layer, on the surfaces of external layers of the beam, exceed the classical ones almost fourfold, while the stresses at the in surfaces between the external and middle layers even change their sign. In analyzing the character of distribution of tangential tresses across the beam thickness, it was found that, according to the nonclassical model, the extreme values arise both in the external layers and in the middle layer, which corresponds to the zero surfaces of normal stresses, whereas in the classical model, an extremum arises only in the middle layer. Moreover, it is seen that this extremum at the center

of the middle layer, according to the classical model, almost twofold exceeds the corresponding value given by the nonclassical model.

Fig. 3. Comparison graphics for w (m), σ (MPa) and τ (MPa) for $l/h = 3$

3. Comparison with experimental data. The results of calculating three-layer beams under uniformly distributed and pointwise loads were compared with experimental data. The strip-beam specimens were symmetric over the height (see Fig. 2) and consisted of layers of an aluminum-magnesium alloy (h_1) and a polystyrene filler (h_2). The geometrical parameters and physic mechanical properties of the layer materials are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3. Characteristics of layers materials of test specimens

Specimen number	b , mm	h_1 , mm	h_2 , mm	E_1 , MPa	E_2 , MPa	G'_1 , MPa	G'_2 , MPa
1	19,9	0,45	10,1	$7 \cdot 10^4$	127	$2,69 \cdot 10^4$	49,6
2	19,8	0,45	10,1	$7 \cdot 10^4$	254	$2,69 \cdot 10^4$	99,2
3	19,7	0,45	10,25	$7 \cdot 10^4$	256	$2,69 \cdot 10^4$	100
4	19,9	0,45	10,1	$7 \cdot 10^4$	179	$2,69 \cdot 10^4$	68,9
5	19,7	0,45	10,1	$7 \cdot 10^4$	197	$2,69 \cdot 10^4$	75,8

The stiffness characteristics of cross sections of the specimens examined, which correspond to the above-mentioned geometrical and physic mechanical characteristics (see

Table 3), and their ratios (4) are presented in Table 4. The fact that these ratios are practically equal confirms the applicability of theoretical preconditions of the model variant suggested.

TABLE 4. Rigidity characteristics of cross sections of specimens

Specimen number	$D_{11}, \text{N}\cdot\text{m}^2$	$D_{12}, \text{N}\cdot\text{m}^4$	$D_{22}, \text{N}\cdot\text{m}^6$	$\frac{D_{12}}{D_{11}}, \text{m}^2$	$\frac{D_{22}}{D_{12}}, \text{m}^2$
1	35,123132	0,113326	$3,658749\cdot 10^{-4}$	0,003227	0,003229
2	35,162534	0,057113	$0,928239\cdot 10^{-4}$	0,001624	0,001625
3	35,996909	0,058892	$0,964076\cdot 10^{-4}$	0,001636	0,001637
4	35,211978	0,082095	$1,915208\cdot 10^{-4}$	0,002331	0,002333
5	34,888535	0,073980	$1,569705\cdot 10^{-4}$	0,002120	0,002122

The specimens were loaded with a pointwise force P applied to the midspan and with a load q uniformly distributed over the upper surface of the beam. The boundary conditions corresponded to a hinge-supported beam in the first case and to a simply supported and rigidly clamped ones in the second case. We should note that, according to conditions (8) and (9), for these cases of fastening, the shear function is determined uniquely from the second equation (7), at its equality to zero at beam ends. Since this function is analogous to the classical beam bending moment, the function χ in both cases is determined by the moment M_{cl}^* in the hinge-supported beam under a given load. The results of theoretical and experimental investigations are shown in Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 5. Data for specimens loaded with a pointwise force P

Specimen number	Length l , mm	Force P , H	Deflections w , mm (at $x = l/2$)			Stresses σ_x , MPa (at $x = l/2 - 50\text{mm}$)		
			w_{cl}	w_{noncl}	w_{exp}	σ_{cl}	σ_{noncl}	σ_{exp}
Hinged ends								
1	300	75	1,201	1,718	1,71	41,1	41,1	39,5
2	300	75	1,200	1,460	1,44	41,0	41,0	38,0
3	300	75	1,172	1,428	1,42	40,6	40,6	39,0
1	200	75	0,356	0,700	0,70	20,5	20,5	19,5
2	200	75	0,355	0,529	0,55	20,5	20,5	19,0
3	200	75	0,347	0,518	0,54	20,3	20,3	19,0

These results show that the deflections obtained by the nonclassical model are more accurate than those following in the classical one: 1.2-2 times for hinge-supported and 2-2.5 times for rigidly clamped beams, which was proved by an experiment. As concerns the stresses, we should point to the rather great relative length of test specimens, $l/h \approx 27$ at $l = 300$ mm and $l/h \approx 18$ at $l = 200$ mm. This is why the values of normal stresses given by the nonclassical and classical models are rather close. Some discrepancy between these results and experimental data can be explained by the fact that the boundary conditions in the experiment, as mentioned in [15], were not satisfied adequately. If we reduce the relative length of the same specimens, i.e. refinement of the stresses at $l/h \approx 10$ and 5 will make up about 10 and 30%, respectively.

TABLE 6. Data for specimens loaded with a uniformly distributed load q

Specimen number	Length l , mm	Force P , H	Deflections w , mm (at $x = l/2$)			Stresses σ_x , MPa (at $x = l/2 - 50$ mm)		
			w_{cl}	w_{noncl}	w_{exp}	σ_{cl}	σ_{noncl}	σ_{exp}
Hinged ends								
1	300	497,5	1,494	2,008	1,99	61,3	62,1	63,5
4	300	497,5	1,490	1,861	1,88	61,2	61,7	61,0
5	300	492,5	1,489	1,826	1,78	61,1	61,6	61,0
Rigidly clamped ends								
1	300	597	0,359	0,976	1,15	24,5	25,4	31,2
4	300	597	0,358	0,802	0,98	24,5	25,1	29,0
5	300	591	0,357	0,761	0,98	24,4	25,0	32,0

Based on the results obtained for hinged and rigidly clamped beams, we can conclude that the reliability of the results according to the variant of the refined model developed is confirmed by experiments. Thus, the results of comparison point to a significant influence of transverse shear deformations on deformations and stresses in three-layer strip-beams, which his most pronounced upon rigid fastening of their ends.

4. Applied problem. Calculation of a statically indeterminate layered multispans beam. For such beams, the variant of the model suggested can be used. Let us assume that, on each support, there is a conditional diaphragm which prevents shear deformations, i.e., $M_{cl}^* = 0$ according to (12), both for end-point (a hinge or rigid clamping) and intermediate supports. Thus, the account of shear deformations in each span is modeled by a moment diagram, according to the classical model, as for 1 single hinge-supported beam.

On this basis, the bending problem for a continuous five-span beam (bridge structure) was solved, whose structure is hown in Fig. 4.

The calculation scheme of the beam under loading and the deflection diagrams are shown in Fig. 5. The deflection diagram according to the nonclassical model (continuous line) is the sum of classical deflections dashed line) and the deflection constituent from shear deformations (dash-dot line). This constituent refines the maximum classical deflection by 17%.

Fig. 4. Structure layered many supported beam

Thus, the suggested variant of the shear analytical model for the stress-strain state of composite layered beams makes it possible to use the known classical results for solving, in the refined statement, bending problems for beams with various boundary conditions and arbitrary loads. The theoretical and experimental investigations performed indicate that the accuracy of the results given by the variant of the nonclassical model is sufficiently high.

Fig. 5. Scheme of calculate and normal displacement of many supported beam

REFERENCES

1. A. K. Noor and W. S. Burton "Assessment of shear deformation theories for multilayered composite plates", Appl. Mech. Rev., 42, No. 1, 1-13 (1989).
2. A. K. Noor and W. S. Burton "Assessment of computational models for multilayered composite shells", Appl. Mech. Rev., 43, No. 4, 67-97 (1990).
3. J. N. Reddy "On the generalization of displacement-based laminated theories," Appl. Mech. Rev., 42, No. 11, Pt. 2, 213-222 (1993).
4. J. N. Reddy and D. H. Robbins "Theories and computational models for composite laminates", Appl. Mech. Rev., 47, No.6, Pt. 1, 21-35 (1994).
5. V.G.Piskunov and A.O.Rasskazov "Development of the theory of layered plates and shells" Prikl .Mekh / 38, N0.2, 22-57 (2002)
6. V.G.Piskunov "An interative analytical theory in the mechanics of layered composite systems", Mech. Compos. Mater., 39 , No 1,1-16 (2003)
7. R.B.Rikards and G.A.Teters. Stability of Shells of Composite Materials (in Russian), Zinatne, Riga (1974).

8. A.O.Rasskazov, I.I.Sokolovskaya, and V.A.Shul'ga. Theory and Calculation of Laminated Orthotropic Plates and Shells, Visha Shkola, Kiev (1986).
9. V.G.Piskunov and V.E.Verizhenko. Linear and Nonlinear Problems Calculating Laminates (in Russian), Budivel'nik, Kiev (1986).
10. V.G.Piskunov, V.E.Verizhenko, V.K.Prisyazhnyuk, V.G.Sipetov and V.S.Karpiljvskii. Calculation of Inhomogeneous Shallow Shells and Plates by the Finite-Element Method, Visha Shkola, Kiev (1987).